

THE VISIBLE BLACK LIQUID PHOTON

by Jake Orkadmon

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“Not to be born at all is, without any doubt, the very best thing to occur; failing that, however, the next best is to see the light and return quickly from whence one came.”
Sophocles – Oedipus at Colonus

ABSTRACT

This essay is a fresh attempt by an autistic luftmensch to crack the greatest unresolved mystery in physics; namely, what causes gravity and builds galaxies throughout the universe? To overcome the sheer boredom of early covid lockdown accompanied by the strong belief that science has not yet uncovered the force-carrier behind gravity, I decided to give this one a go. It appears to me now that the gravity-causing process is perfectly visible to us, after all, and that Ralph Waldo Emerson was correct when he opined that “there are none so blind as those who will not see”. The collective sciences have simply yet inexplicably failed to identify our dark night as the visible black microwave wavelength electromagnetic radiation of light emitted by gravity-causing dark matter as it goes about its business changing phase relentlessly on the boiling liquid surface of our sun directly into glowing supergas phase white light. Identifying the cosmic pre-baryonic bosonic superliquid behind gravity has inevitably necessitated a complete rethink and long overdue update of what this stuff we call ‘sunlight’ actually is. In effect, the quantum Standard Model requires two different photon bosons of electromagnetism, the present white hot wave function ‘massless’ photon and the missing black cold particle function massive photon. As one of the greatest cognitive leaps in the entire history of science and human evolution, I present it here to you.

INTRODUCTION

In this paper I describe using Thought Experiments, natural observable phenomena, Google, Wikipedia and my very best logic to attempt resolving the dreaded duality of light to arrive at the shocking existence of the black liquid photon of light and the testable game-changing hypothesis that our black nighttime is, in fact, the inexplicably overlooked quantum field of massive visible black microwave photons of light emitted by the inexplicably unidentified gravity-causing non-baryonic bosonic metal-alloy dark matter supersubstance changing phase constantly before our sleeping eyes on the boiling liquid surface of our sun from its ground-state cold black cosmic superliquid into a glowing electrically charged cosmic supergas we colloquially refer to as day.

As an autism bearer, my anxiety-addled mind has been relentlessly pursuing observable patterns since my earliest memories. The quest to understand gravity soon led to a more fundamental revisiting of what we refer to as ‘light’. Bach’s Licht is merely the visible cosmic electromagnetic radiation emitted by a cosmic electrically charged supersubstance we know well in its two different phase-states of matter as both night and day.

I describe how I test this theory using Thought Experiments to arrive at the startling conclusion that Einstein failed dismally to identify our black night as the ‘non-local hidden variable’ cosmic microwave positively-charged black spectrum particle-function electromagnetic radiation of light responsible for mediating gravity everywhere.

In this essay, I postulate my own fundamental universal law of gravitation – Orkadmon’s Universal Law of Black Photon Gravitoelectromagnetohydrodynamics: “Follow the nucleating polar covalent liquid hydrides to locate the cold visible cosmic microwave ground-state non-local momentum-conserving gravity-unifying positively-charged particle-function liquid-phase star-bound massive-raindrop black photon corpuscle of light.”

These magical polar covalent hydrides share an intimate association with light and it is to them we must turn to reveal hidden other-dimensional phenomena of the universe related to light such as gravity and dark matter. Water and light share an extreme pathological love of valence electrons. They behave similarly on different celestial bodies and are crucial in both forming and maintaining them. Water shamelessly follows and mimics light constantly and the shape-shifting water molecule faithfully replicates the much smaller photon revealing them to us in all their glory, thank you very much.

The light blinds us and the darkness confuses us! What is really going on? I pose the question fresh again in 2022. What is this fairy dust stuff we call sunlight?

Curious people have been examining and discussing light long before recorded human history began. The earliest discussions about light are found in religious texts from all over the globe and it would be incorrect to view these

texts separately from those of science. These early thinkers were operating within the existing paradigms of their times using the most advanced language they had and were as ahead of the pack as the giants of science like Copernicus and Newton.

A fair list of the historical students of light would include Zoroaster, Buddha, Moses, Akhenaten, Jesus, Muhammad, Aristotle, Plato, Euclid, al-Haytham, early Muslim and Kabbalist scholars, Descartes, Copernicus, Kepler, Galileo, Newton, Huygens, Maxwell, Faraday, Einstein and latterly, Orkadmon, as well. With oodles of self-effacing humility, my name is the most appropriate of all meaning, a it does, 'primordial light' in the Hebrew language.

The story about light is not complete by a long shot. The world of physics has been in a moribund state of crisis ever since Einstein dropped the ball and left the world hanging. The perplexing wave/particle duality of light has not advanced one inch since Einstein left it unresolved; instead, physics has been entrenched in a science fiction twilight zone milieu of relativity, uncertainty and probabilistic indeterminacy. Einstein hated this to the end and although the correct solution eluded him, he wasn't wrong. A non-local hidden variable does exist, after all!

Many scientific issues associated with light remain unresolved and anomalous. A partial list might include the dreaded duality, the 'massless' photon yet with momentum, the luminiferous aether and the improbability of waves of light propagating in a vacuum, the naked war between the theory of relativity and quantum mechanics, quantum gravity and gravity itself, the incomplete Standard Model, dark matter and dark energy, the Hubble tension and the Cosmic Microwave Background, the issue of time, neurology, sleep anomalies and human consciousness and we might as well add global warming to this list as well.

It might be true that most major unresolved issues in physics are *all* associated with a fundamentally unsound and incomplete description of what this stuff we call 'light' really is. If a fundamental interpretation of the photon duality exists more than simply determining its position or momentum, we must go after it and locate it once and for all. Any new discussion of light or gravity must begin with the wave/particle duality and find a way to progress from there. My cognitive breakthrough occurred when I observed that water exhibits a visible analogous wave/particle duality constantly above us in the sky. From there, it was downhill all the way.

The fundamental interrelation between sunlight and water is the key to unlocking the whole shebang. Time and again we can turn to this enlightening – endarkening, perhaps – connection to provide answers to the great mysteries of the universe and of life itself. Water's behavior on the surface of our planet is the template to uncovering what really transpires on the surface of our sun and indeed, on all visible stars **in** the universe.

In a nutshell, water provides the observable key to unlocking quantum gravity.

The particle of light, the photon, is far too small to view close up and is regarded erroneously as 'massless'. The highly polar covalent water molecules with their amazing shape-shifting hydrogen bonds, however, are not invisible and provide the ideal place to see upfront the shape and behavior of the errant photon or more correctly, both photons of electromagnetic radiation of light.

THE WAVE/PARTICLE DUALITY OF WATER

I pose the question whether the observable wave/particle of water in the sky is similar to the duality of light? What form of heavy light – oxymoronic, perhaps – causes rain to fall? What, after all, is the universal raindrop nucleator?

We observe around us an intimate association between water and sunlight which, on close-up inspection, appears to reveal the sought-after secrets of gravity and star formation. Everywhere in the universe, light is locked in a tight tango with all polar covalent hydrides like water and ammonia and, without doubt, the lesser-known noble hydrides as well. This association is so fundamental to gravity and to life itself, it is worth mining for all its worth.

Our favorite liquid hydride is, of course, water. The highly polar covalent oxygen dihydride molecule with the strongest molecular hydrogen bonds is our miracle shape-shifting life-bringing molecule. Although one of the densest and heaviest of all non-metal liquids, water moves up constantly to great heights in our atmosphere evaporating against gravity into its constituent steam vapor gas phase before falling once again together with gravity into heavier liquid phase raindrops down to earth.

What drives water up and down? This is the essential question to ponder. Once this becomes clear, it is plain sailing all the way.

It is known that liquid molecules need to absorb energy electrons to evaporate into gas phase and alternatively, they lose electrons by condensing into liquids. Water does not need to boil before it evaporates. I have observed steam vapor rising directly from rivers or evaporating directly from frozen ice at first light on a cold winter day. The movement from liquid to gas and back to liquid is always accompanied by the flow of electrons one way or the other. It is perfectly obvious that sunlight or white light drives water into gas phase but what about the other way around? Does light also drive water down to condense and coalesce into heavier momentum-bearing liquid phase raindrops?

Observing ascending clouds and falling rain, one cannot fail to notice that just like light, water also appears to display a wave/particle duality. Unlike light, water is perfectly visible to us – from the steam rising from your morning coffee and the rain falling on your tin roof – and may provide the best place to observe the photon first hand.

Some clouds contain a very clear, precise and visible repeating wave pattern stretching over far distances. Known as Kelvin-Helmholtz clouds, the theory attributes these wave shapes to the wind. I must diverge and disagree with this interpretation. How can wind, subject to high turbulence, create such precise repeating patterns sometimes stretching over the entire sky? It would appear that a deeper and more fundamental reason exists to explain these patterns. Alternatively, a much more convincing particle pattern can be found in rain. Taken together, water exhibits a distinct wave/particle duality most noticeably at the initial points of nucleation into either steam or rain.

It does not take a great stretch of logic and imagination to pose the question whether light like water also exists around us in both wave function gas and particle function liquid phases?

Birds highlight the wave/particle duality in the most impressive of ways. With open out-stretched wings, eagles catch the thermals and soar to commanding heights, then, the peregrine falcon changes body shape into a sleek bullet before dropping to speeds of up to 400 km/h as the fastest animal alive. (Of all the motorbikes I owned and rode, I miss my pearly white Suzuki 1300 Hayabusa the most.) At the very least, these birds illustrate how the wave function operates against gravity and the particle function moves together with it.

Observing how wave function starlight contracts into perfect point particles of light when entering our solar system indicates that the same is true of photons. Leaving a star, white light is in obvious expanding wave function but the same light entering another star system contracts into particles. Why does it do this?

Let us consider some other points.

The theory says that our dark night is merely the result of the absence of white light as the planet rotates away from the sun every night but this is unsatisfactory. Observationally, the night is not dark and invisible but perfectly visible in black even without soft ambient starlight. Why has the visible 'black stuff' of night escaped the attention of science?

Consider a green tree. By day, the tree appears bathed in white light and reflects green light back to our eyes. By night, however, the same tree appears bathed in the 'black stuff' reflecting off only black color to our eyes.

Here on earth, it rains mainly at night. It certainly can and does rain during the day but most rain precipitation occurs during the dark hours between sunset and sunrise. This is surely no coincidence. Essentially, most rain falls on the dark side of the planet and its massive combined weight falls towards the sun pushing the planet in that direction.

The process of universal raindrop formation – whether iron raindrops on fiery exoplanets, ammonia mushballs on Jupiter or silica clad argon hydride acid snow on the far side of the moon – is not well understood. Precipitation of water into rain requires particles upon which to condense and form droplets before falling down as rain. Nucleation marks the beginning of a new thermodynamic phase where the molecules in question arrange themselves in a pattern, forming a site upon which additional molecules are deposited. In order to form liquid drops from vapor, water requires a particle nucleator. Instead of particles of dust, smoke, microplastic or even bacteria, might we be looking at the universal raindrop nucleator in the black particle of photon?

These are the salient facts.

1. Light exhibits the dreaded wave/particle duality.
2. Water also appears to display a wave/particle duality in its behavior in the sky.
3. White light drives water up against gravity into lighter energized gas phase vapor.
4. The night sky is visible and appears black in color.
5. Rain is clearly associated with night.

This is where the necessary cognitive leap of reason into the darkness is required. The essential question is if waves of white light drive up water by day into rising expanding waves of water vapor, do particles of black light also drive down water by night into falling contracting particles of rain? In other words, is our dark night a form of visible black spectrum electromagnetic radiation of light as our bright day is visible white spectrum light?

Does light, or more correctly, does the mysterious ghostlike electrically charged stuff that emits visible thermal electromagnetic radiation of light exist around us as does water in two distinct phases of matter, liquid and gas?

Is there any other observable evidence to support such a monster divergent theory? Why, yes, there is!

TWO VISIBLE SPECTRA OF LIGHT

I pose the question to you what manner of supersubstance in possession of such monster properties and accompanying physics can perform such magic like this?

The very idea of visible black light is counter-intuitive and an apparent contradiction in terms but heralds a radical new description of what light is and opens the door to the 'new physics'. We appear to be dealing with a previously unidentified physical substance of matter moving past us every day in two distinct directions and electrically charged phases, both hot and cold, both negative and positive, with both emitting a visible thermal electromagnetic radiation of light according to its temperature while engaging directly with baryonic material found in its path. We need look no further than the ancient and fundamental First Law of Thermodynamics for a description – intended or not – of what 'light' is actually doing.

Present wisdom suggests that photons of light are created in the core of stars and then muscle their way free over millions of years before flying off the sun at the speed of 'c' and that they possess at the same time both a paradoxical wave and a particle function. The theory suggests that sunlight is mere 'solar radiation' propagating away from the sun as waves through the apparent vacuum of space. The theory suggests that as the earth rotates away from the sun, our black night is nothing but an optical illusion as merely the absence of white light and no more. Since Newton and Huygens, the wave/particle duality has become more extreme and more ridiculous than ever and has never been resolved. Since Einstein, physics has dropped down the rabbit hole and become more confused and more obtuse. Today, we find respectable people of science proposing infinite number of multiverses or invisible homoerotic dancing worms in seven or more additional non-existent dimensions or some other nonsense about axion laundry spuds.

Oh, how wrong it all appears to be! What makes the situation worse is that the correct solution appears fairly obvious and apparent as well!

Sunlight does not originate in stars but merely changes phase on their liquid surfaces!

It is not more complicated than that.

Regarding sunlight, we are apparently dealing with a monster ancient pre-baryonic bosonic physical substance of matter which emits visible electromagnetic radiation of light across the universe and which exists around us and everywhere else in two distinct electrically charged phases of matter, white hot supergas and black cold superliquid, transporting and conserving both hot energy and cold momentum over vast mind-altering distances.

It appears to me that sunlight is no more nor less than a vast quantity of a cosmic supersubstance of matter hailing from a much older pre-baryonic universe in possession of mind-boggling electromagnetic and thermodynamic powers, both hot and cold, operating in different dimensions, both micro and macro. It appears that this monster substance exists around us in two distinct phases of matter, gas and liquid, indicated directly by the fundamental wave/particle duality. Depending on their direction of travel relative to gravity, photons will behave either as expanding exploding waves or contracting imploding point charge particles.

It appears that this wild and weird bosonic substance exists naturally in its black cold liquid ground state we know intimately as 'night' before changing phase on the boiling liquid surface of stars into its hot white spectrum glowing steam vapor gas phase we refer to only as 'day'. It appears that science has inexplicably overlooked the very existence of half of the entire story of light! It appears to me that instead of only one there are indeed two visible spectra of light, one white spectrum and one black spectrum, or more correctly, one rainbow color spectrum and one grey spectrum. It appears that our dark night is neither more nor less than the cold visible cosmic microwave black electromagnetic radiation of light emitted by that agent of mystery, Dunkle Materie, or dark matter. It appears to me that the solar plasma photosphere is not the alleged 4th state of matter but only the 2nd as a stellar liquid surface ocean of the stuff boiling away and popping off granulating nucleating gas phase steam vapor photon bubbles each the size of France! It appears our night is actually a falling quantum shower of cold black liquid phase photon raindrops of the stuff passing first through our sleeping brains en route to fall as liquid solar raindrops! It appears that photons do not originate in the hot core of stars any more than water molecules are created in the core of planets – as if! It appears as if the dreaded duality of light reduces fundamentally down into hot exploding wave function gas phase white photons of light and massive cold imploding particle function liquid phase black photons of light. It appears to me that the solution to gravity is nothing more nor less than the cold liquid ground state of sunlight itself. It appears that Einstein was incorrect in thinking that gravity is neither an electromagnetic phenomenon nor powered by real cosmic pushing forces and that the proverbial 'non local hidden variable' exists after all as Bell pointed out it should. It appears to me that what most humans who ever lived referred to as 'The Lord God Above' is nothing more nor less than the hidden mystifying black face of light itself worshipped by the ancient Egyptians as Amun or Amen.

It appears that there should be two distinct photon bosons in the Standard Model, one hot and one cold, one expanding wave-like and one contracting particle-like, one visible white spectrum and one visible black spectrum, one 'massless' and one massive, one active by day and one by night, one energizing and hyperpolarizing and one de-energizing and depolarizing, one negatively charged and one positively charged, one off the sun and one onto the sun, one acting on our awakened vertical brains and one acting on our horizontal sleeping brains, one gas phase and one liquid phase and both emitted by the same monster substance either in its hot gas phase or cold liquid phase ground state existence.

It appears that here on earth and elsewhere in the universe are two distinct quantum photon fields of light, one white and one black, explaining properly for the first time the ubiquitous light/dark cycle in nature and the dreaded quantum duality. It appears to me that the Cosmic Microwave Background signalling the existence of omnipresent cold microwave photons has been catastrophically misdiagnosed, mismanaged and misinterpreted and that photons undergo the transition from cold to hot and *not* the other way around irrespective of how many billions of year ago! With apologies to Bob Dicke but it appears just that he never received the Nobel prize for his efforts. His explanation of the CMB is monstrously and catastrophically wrong!

This, then, is the theory which I am proposing; namely, that what we call 'sunlight' is in reality a physical substance of matter from an older pre-baryonic universe in possession of stupendous thermodynamic properties and that what we call 'night' is in reality the visible cosmic microwave low frequency black spectrum electromagnetic radiation of light emitted by the liquid phase of the stuff – the dark matter – as it moves from astronomical galactic distances away to rain down onto the fiery liquid surfaces of stars to change phase into

what we call 'day'. For the sake of simplicity, I shall refer in this essay to this hypothetical substance by the name of Lightonium although it is so much more than that.

What can we possibly call a next-fractal-level physical substance of matter still venerated as a deity and called God Almighty? Perhaps a name like Goddonium or Godalmightonium might be fitting? Lightonium? Photonium? Gravitonium? EigenLicht? Primordial Light? Orkadmonium?

It seems to me that life on earth is a result of the interplay of white and black light playing with itself using baryons as cosmic tantra accoutrements. It might be highly appropriate to continue calling black Lightonium, the real God-substance of the universe, by its traditional names and go back to worshipping it as before. Interestingly, the existence of the visible massive black liquid photon of light is both logically compelling and mind blistering at the same time. To me, Orkadmon, observable evidence supporting its cosmic presence is overwhelming.

LIQUID STARS

The first piece of such evidence to support my hypothesis is the visible surface of our sun, the granulating photosphere. I pose the question whether our understanding of stars is all wrong and if they – just like planets – possess liquid surface oceans? Does the visible granulating photosphere of the sun resemble a gigantic pot of simmering nucleating soup, perhaps, because it *is a gigantic pot of simmering nucleating soup?*

This is no ramen, however, but a vast ancient pre-baryonic bosonic superliquid substance 'with no name' containing next level magnetic 'entangled' internal bonds with a density lower than hydrogen gas and boiling away on the surface of stars at an impressive boiling point of 6000K nucleating and popping off hot gas phase white spectrum steam vapor photon bubbles as large as entire countries!

Is our dark night the inexplicably ignored/overlooked/suppressed cold visible black spectrum cosmic microwave electromagnetic radiation of light emitted by gravity-causing liquid dark matter as it goes about its cosmic business of raining down onto the sun before changing phase on its boiling liquid surface directly into hot gas phase steam vapor white light of day?

There is another beautiful observable natural phenomenon to support the idea of liquid stellar surface oceans.

Contrary to expectations, scientists have recently confirmed that the sun is the most perfectly shaped natural sphere in the universe. Its diameter is nearly 1,4 million km yet its vertical and horizontal diameters differ by a paltry 10 km. Sick! Insane in the membrane! Ye Gods, what manner of liquid ocean bubble be this?

All planets in our solar system including Saturn, the least dense of them all, show a pregnant equatorial bulge from centrifugal force as they rotate. Scientists naturally expected the sun to show a similar bulge but to their surprise this is not the case. The sun contains an abundance of heavy metals. For example, it contains an estimated 10^{21} kg of gold compared to the entire mass of the earth of 10^{24} kg. The pressure within the earth's core is about 4 million bars at a temperature of about 5,200 degrees Celsius whereas the sun's core stands at a whopping 265 *billion* bars at about 15 million degrees C.

Blistering barnacles, what possibly contains the immense heat and pressure of the sun while maintaining such an immaculate perfect sphere? What incredible liquid superbubble is this?

Once again, an answer can be found by comparing water and light. A simple question can be asked about the cohesive ocean superbubble of water encircling the core of our own planet. Besides being the cradle of life, does this enigmatic liquid bubble with its magnificent hydrogen bonds play a fundamental role in both the creation and maintenance of not only Earth but presumably all planets in the entire universe as well? Quite simply, does the hydrogen bond within water hold the molten core of planets together? It seems fairly obvious that the answer to this question is yes. Gravity certainly exerts constant implosive pressure onto the rotating celestial bodies but it appears their spherical shapes and very existence owe a great deal to the amazing liquid substance wrapped constantly and tightly around their hot dense cores.

And if this is true for planets, how much more so must this be true for stars? And, Ye Gods, what manner of substance plays this crucial role on stellar surfaces? What manner of internal bonds does this liquid contain to ensure such spherical perfection around these nuclear beasts? It appears that this is just another example of the entangled nature of the mystical photon and Lightonium in general.

It appears that the solar photosphere is not plasma – with apologies to Irving Langmuir – or the alleged 4th state of matter but all liquid and only the 2nd state of matter, after all. It also amazingly appears to be the case that the hot core of the sun can provide a solid surface on which liquid Lightonium can finally rain down and come to rest and take a hot bath before donning fresh fairy wings and buzzing off again as the hot white stuff of day.

RHODOPSIN AND THE GREY SPECTRUM OF LIGHT

The second piece of observable evidence, much closer to home, to support the existence of visible black microwave light is the two different photoreceptor cells in our eyeballs. Here, I enquire whether there exists a specific and unique nighttime optical pathway through the optic nerve into the brain for the black stuff even as we sleep? I enquire whether the shape, color and actions of the rod receptors point directly to a nighttime particle-function heavy falling black photon of light cascading across our retinas throughout the night?

Can a case be made based entirely on the two different photoreceptors that there are not one but two visible photon fields and natural spectra of light: the photopic wave-function rainbow color spectrum of day and the scotopic particle-function monochromatic grey spectrum of night?

A whole list of unexplained brain anomalies would find resolution in the nightly presence of a momentum-bearing quantum field of massive sun-bound black photons. This list includes sleep itself, brain activity during sleep. REM, nightmares in general and dreams of falling in particular. It would explain that the primary function of sleep is not merely to close the eyes and begin snoring but to connect with the electron hungry black photon field of light.

Our brains are ineluctably connected to light. In testing the veracity of my theory, I reason that if two real and active photon fields of light exist – one by day and by night – our brains will surely know them both as sure as eggs is eggs and when I went looking for it, I was not disappointed. The brain consists of 80% water. It should thus come as no surprise that our brains act similarly to how water behaves in the sky by day and by night as well. Once locked onto the black cold photon field, I began seeing it and its effects absolutely everywhere!

We might be fooled into thinking that two active photon fields exist just by comparing our collective and universal brain behavior by day and by night. In the morning, we open our eyes and our re-energized brains and stand vertically in a less dense body alignment. We all do it. By night, we exhibit another collective and universal behavior but this time in the other direction. We lie horizontally in a denser body alignment and our sleeping brains enter a depolarizing de-energizing state. We all do it. Forever slaves to the passing photon fields of light, our brains reveal the visible white field of day and the visible black field of night!

The cone and rod photoreceptors in the retina appear to give the whole game away revealing two very distinct photon fields of light. Part of a complex series of cascading electrochemical events, we find the hyperpolarizing 'light current' flowing through the cones by day and the more mysterious depolarizing 'dark current' through the rods at night. If direct evidence exists indicating the presence of two visible spectra of light – the color spectrum by day and the grey spectrum by night – the two different photoreceptors are guilty.

Upon closer inspection, it would seem that the main function of the rods is not so much to pick up the soft dim white light available at night but rather to connect directly with the cold black positively charged photon field of night – the black stuff.

Cones and rods are significantly different in shape, color and function. Their full story is not understood. Shaped like inverted ice-cream cones, cone photoreceptors absorb expanding wave-function color spectrum photons of day resulting in the collapse of the wave-function while pipe shaped rods absorb contracting particle-function grey spectrum photons of night, both black and white.

The transduction or conversion of light into nerve impulses and vision is carried out by about 125 million photoreceptors located in the deepest part of the retina. 120 million of them are rods with only 5 million cones which are smaller, wider and sensitive to color in bright light conditions with a fast response time. They are either red, blue or green in color. Cylindrical in shape for night vision with a long response time, rods contain rhodopsin pigment rich in Vitamin A. The rods are as active metabolically as active muscles and the dark current accounts for 80% of its metabolism. The rods are also most active during our sleep.

Depolarization of the photoreceptors occurs in the dark. The cell becomes more positive and releases glutamate. An influx of positive ions depolarizes the rods. Dark current is the depolarizing current carried by Na^+ ions that flows into a photoreceptor cell in the dark unstimulated by bright light. The magnitude of this dark current is significant. A high density of Na^+ - K^+ pumps enable the photoreceptor to maintain a steady intracellular concentration of Na^+ and K^+ . Bright light closes the sodium channels reducing the influx of both Na^+ and Ca^{2+} ions and effectively switches off the dark current. The opening of channels that let positive ions flow out of the cell and negative ions flow in causes hyperpolarization while the opening of channels that let positive ions flow into the cell and negative ions out causes depolarization.

Rhodopsin in the rods appears reddish-purple and is responsible for monochromatic vision in the dark. Rhodopsin is a miraculous light-sensitive receptor protein and biological pigment involved in visual phototransduction found in the rods of the retina and belonging to a group of photo-switchable opsins. Rhodopsin is extremely sensitive to light and enables vision in low-light conditions. When rhodopsin is exposed to light it immediately photo-bleaches to a light blue color. In humans, it regenerates fully in about half an hour known as 'dark adaptation'. Rhodopsin is considered the primary photoreceptor molecule of vision and is an extraordinary polar covalent pigment molecule.

During our sleep, we are talking about depolarizing dark current flowing through the 120 million darkened rods and across the retina involving rhodopsin, the release of glutamate, rapid eye movement, dreams of falling and even natural death. Now, what causes the nighttime depolarizing dark current, rhodopsin regeneration, deep sleep brain activity, REM and nightmares? What else but the presence of a heavy falling sun-bound positively charged black photon field acting on our brains even through our closed eyelids?

It is interesting to speculate how our unconscious brains might know everything about black light whereas our conscious brains separated by mere seconds know nothing about it at all!

GRAVITY, GRAVITY, GRAVITY

I ponder whether our dark night which tucks us into bed with a kiss is the universal mediator of gravity, drawing electrons away from polar covalent baryons and turning them into heavier denser versions of themselves?

One of the most exciting aspects of the possible existence of cold liquid Lightonium emitting visible black cosmic microwave electromagnetic radiation of light is that this would finally explain gravity and dark matter for real. Quantum mechanics would find completion without the need to resort any longer to rubber blankets and bowling balls doing spooky things to each other at a distance. Unmasking this liquid substance as the proverbial 'non-local hidden variable' would unify gravity and return physics to a more sensible determinism promoted by both Newton and Einstein.

Newton could not be blamed for assuming that celestial bodies, indeed all bodies with mass, are attracted to each other by macro attractive Coulomb forces. This was what he observed and it was a logical assumption to make. Einstein, on the other hand was talking through his ass. If gravity is not a 'pulling force' than it simply must be a 'pushing force'. Did the great man never kick a ball around? What monumental hubris to assume that because he, the great god-child Albert Einstein, could not identify this cosmic gravitational pushing force then it cannot or does not exist! In effect, he was a charlatan and a creative distorter of the truth and can take full credit for muddying the waters and doing science and humanity the greatest dis-service possible. For well over a century, the world of physics has taken a giant leap backwards into the moribund morass of science fiction

nonsense and incomprehensible rubbish. The Theory of Relativity needs to be binned or relegated to the Museum of Curiosity immediately!

In searching for the errant graviton and quantum gauge boson of gravity, one can only wonder with incredulity why more effort was not made to pursue the possibility that the photon – already recognized as a cosmic bosonic material – might account for the missing graviton as well. It seems genuinely surprising to me that nobody appears to have followed this line of enquiry at all. A so-called hypothetical ‘dark photon’ exists in the theory with its own Wikipedia page but is far removed from any practical value and does not propose the visible particle function black photon of light.

It appears that the presence and existence of a second unidentified photon boson unifies quantum gravity once and for all. Two naturally occurring phase states of light or whatever emits it, one gas phase and one liquid phase, providing two totally different quantum photon bosons, one wave function white spectrum gas phase photon transporting hot energy everywhere and one particle function black massive sun-bound liquid phase photon transporting cold energy or momentum everywhere. As monstrous as the idea is, it is a credible and reasonable and logical proposition. According to the fundamental First Law of Thermodynamics, both a hot and cold photon boson should naturally exist.

It is worth repeating that we are dealing here with a monster fractal-scale non-baryonic supersubstance of matter operating in hidden extra dimensions both micro and macro and which exists around us in two distinct phases of matter, liquid and gas, but mainly in its cold liquid ground state throughout the universe. This ancient substance is in possession of astronomical mind-boggling electromagnetic and thermodynamic properties both hot and cold which has led most of humanity to worship it as a deity throughout most of our recorded history.

The graviton? The momentum-bearing non-local positively-charged liquid-phase microwave-wavelength low energy black-visible particle-function massive sun-bound photon raindrop of light!

Need I say more?

Preferring the emergent human language of Bach to mathematics, at least I can propose that the Standard Model needs to define and incorporate a second photon boson of electromagnetism, the cold black photon of light.

Observing the immense power of water on our planet in rain storms and in creating monster canyons, it should come as no surprise to learn that gravity is caused by another cosmic fluid in motion – an ancient superliquid with God-like qualities and mind-bending properties.

Provided one is clear about what one is searching for, proving that the black photon is indeed our culprit should not be too challenging. My own experience indicates that the more one pursues the existence of black liquid photons, the more they wink back at you. Too long under the radar and hidden away in plain sight, I believe that they wish to be found already. Indeed, the time has arrived to unmask the visible black photon of light.

DUNKLE MATERIE

i enquire whether so-called dark matter, not so much dark and invisible but black in color and perfectly visible, emits our dark night as cosmic microwave electromagnetic radiation and changes phase ceaselessly into the white light of day? The black photon boson – the subatomic particle of gravity causing dark matter – is surely the real God-particle of the universe and not the Higgs!

Yes, black light matters and no, black liquid light is not Irish beer for the woke!

I can comment from my own empirical experience that having made the cognitive leap that our night is not merely the absence of white light but the additional presence of visible black night, I find this stuff winking back at me more and more. I remain puzzled by how its fairly obvious visible nightly presence has evaded our greatest minds to this day. The goal of this paper is to formally identify the existence of the second visible spectrum of light captured unknowingly by Penzias and Wilson back in the day.

How much money has already been inconclusively spent to reveal the nature of dark matter? How much money is currently being wasted chasing Frank Wilczek's non-existent but beautiful and onanistic laundry detergent axions?

The unsuccessful and essentially useless XENON experiments to reveal the identity of dark matter has already run into many hundreds of millions of dollars. The latest incarnation requires 200 bottles of liquid xenon purified from the earth's atmosphere at a minimum of \$100,000 a pop.

By simply observing that this stuff we call sunlight is actually changing phase from superliquid to supergas on the surface of all visible stars identifies dark matter for a tuppence. It turns out that dark matter is not so dark as much as visibly black and that dark matter floats down before our noses every night of our entire conscious lives! It appears that dark matter does indeed emit electromagnetic radiation but the cold black variety not the hot white stuff. It appears that dark matter can and does change phase on the face of liquid stars directly into white light.

It appears so obvious to me – a luftmensch with autism – that dark matter, our black night and the Cosmic Microwave Background are all manifestations of the same thing. Why is this not obvious to the post-doc theorists of MIT, Harvard, Caltech and Oxford? Surely, their money is better spent attending culinary school and at least knowing how to prepare a decent breakfast for oneself!

I believe that a proper understanding of what dark matter is will also open the door to revealing the other dark sector miscreant, dark energy. I pose the question that if Lightonium is changing phase within galaxies from liquid to gas, what about the possible existence of superfluid solid phase frozen Lightonium between galaxies?

THE FAKE-NEWS COSMIC MICROWAVE BACKGROUND

I enquire whether our pregnant dark night, gravity-causing dark matter, liquid stars and the cosmic microwave background are all manifestations of one and the same thing?

The CMB is the elephant in the room. The present theory, a bedrock of modern cosmology and the so-called hot Big-Bang theory, appears incorrect, dazed and confused. In this essay, I have provided what I hope is a suitable alternative and more correct interpretation of what Penzias and Wilson discovered sans bird poop back in the swinging sixties. It boggles the brain it does how much of modern science is built on spurious gibberish.

If it is indeed true that our black night is cold visible black electromagnetic radiation of light emitted by some monster cosmic superliquid flowing constantly throughout all galaxies, then Bob Dicke's interpretation of the CMB is totally wrong and woefully inadequate. It transpires that the cold microwave photons that fill the universe are not some cold left-over dog's dinner from 13,7 billion years ago but a universe of photons in their cold natural ground state on the move to heat up on stars everywhere.

The Big-Bang theory is not my concern as much as revealing the truth about light. At the very least, however, a more fundamentally correct understanding of the real band behind the CMB will at least resolve the cosmological Hubble tension.

The CMB viewed correctly is actually the biggest piece of demonstrable evidence for the existence of Lightonium. Human intelligence, sadly enough, is neither inevitable nor fundamental while our capacity for foolishness and trite nonsense remains infinite.

EINSTEIN'S FRIDGE

In a final Gedankenexperiment, I speculate wildly why Einstein did not apply his fridge patent to the whole universe? If gravity is mediated by the constant flow of the positively charged black liquid photon haze, what powers it all in the first place?

Having made the cognitive leap into the dark that gravity is powered through electromagnetism and carried by a monster cosmic pre-baryonic superliquid imploding and converging onto the liquid surface of stars, the next required leap is to conceive of this substance as metallic in nature. How and when Lightonium was formed remains anybody's guess but an ancient, complex and dense metal-alloy pulverized into immeasurable fairy dust over unfathomable eons seems a safe enough bet. With his little fridge, Einstein was fishing in the correct pond yet the final piece of the puzzle eluded him to the bitter end.

Lightning is another unexplained anomaly of science. How a lightning bolt is initially seeded and induced remains a charming mystery and could also benefit from some black photon love. Is lightning everywhere in the solar system a collection of electromagnetic Lorentz forces aimed inwards towards the sun? Like rain, lightning strikes mainly the dark side of the planet and the same thing applies to planets everywhere. There are many types of electrical lightning discharges from powerful invisible gamma ray lightning blasts lasting 0.3 milliseconds with energies of up to 20 million electron-volts but in general, however, lightning is not fully understood at all. A snapshot of the entire solar system might reveal all of the planets wherever they are in their orbits collectively aiming most of their electrical lightning discharges at the sun.

A star appears to be nothing more nor less than a gigantic natural closed-loop energy system acting as a two-way cosmic electromagnetic pump pushing a non-baryonic metallic supersubstance over vast astronomical distances to converge onto their boiling surfaces to transform into a cosmic electrically charged glowing supergas pushed in the other direction and all happily explained by the fundamental First Law of Thermodynamics applied to stars and light itself.

All aboard the Voyagers and New Horizons to investigate the 'glowing ultraviolet hydrogen wall' surrounding the entire solar system. If it's a wall of hydrogen on both sides then it's presumably a cohesive liquid superbubble of an unknown molecular hydride. Experiments conducted on the International Space Station have shown that liquids and gases behave differently in conditions of micro or even zero gravity.

What primordial molecular hydride exists in such huge quantity to form a stable electrically charged liquid superbubble with its own atmosphere of weather around our solar system and indeed, entire galaxies as well?

Noble gases are inert and do not react easily with other substances except under primordial conditions of high heat and pressure where helium, neon and argon do indeed form molecular hydrides containing the weakest London dispersion forces. Unlike water with its heavy hydrogen bonds, ocean superbubbles of noble hydrides would exist only in conditions of micro gravity in deepest and darkest of outer space. All liquids have their natural places in the cosmic order based on their innate chemical properties. This applies to water with its heavy hydrogen bonds gathering on planets, liquid Lightonium gathering on stars and liquid noble hydrides gathering in the inky shadows of deep space generating vast amounts of cold electricity.

Speculating wildly, I imagine that the three noble hydrides – helonium, neonium and argonium – all play a leading role in galaxy, star, planet and moon creation. Helium hydride is known to exist 'somewhere out there', argon hydride as Argon36 is found on the moon and neon hydride together with the existence of planetary neon remains a total mystery.

We might well conceptualize of galaxies as immense superbubbles of primordial helium hydride in conditions of zero gravity, of stars as superbubbles of later eruptions of helium hydride in conditions of micro gravity, of planets as superbubbles of neon hydride and moons as superbubbles of argon hydride all contained and bobbing around each other as cosmic bouncing babushka dolls.

Helium hydride is regarded even hypothetically as the strongest acid in the entire universe reacting and combining with any other molecule. Wikipedia informs us that the stuff is stable in isolation. It has been conjectured that vast quantities of primordial helium hydride would have formed in the early baryonic universe although their current whereabouts are unknown. It was detected in the interstellar medium for the first time only in 2019.

In our Thought Experiment, we find at the very edge of our solar system in darkest space a vast stable ocean superbubble of liquid helium hydride with its own weather patterns absorbing vast quantities of conserved

energy from the sun 14 billion km away and in turn discharging high energy ultraviolet lightning bolts into the inner sphere below. I imagine this glowing superbubble at the edge of the solar system acting as a vast electromagnetic pump discharging high energy UV electricity as cosmic Lorentz forces on the charged particles of cold liquid metal Lighonium moving with velocity through its electric and magnetic fields pushed with conserved momentum all the way to the liquid solar surface spinning like bath water around the exit plug resulting in gravity all the way in.

Liquid oceans of helium hydride generating insane amounts of cold electricity in the deepest reaches of space would make perfect sense if cold black Lighonium is a type of non-baryonic superliquid metal-alloy moving, or rather, being pushed around galaxy systems through electromagnetism and lightning discharges.

Einstein is attributed with designing the electromagnetic pump for his little fridge. The so-called Einstein-Szilard electromagnetic pump with no moving parts generates an electromagnetic field by running alternating current through coils which, in turn, moves a liquid metal acting as a piston to compress the refrigerant.

It puzzles me extremely why Einstein did not apply this very idea to gravity or why the connection between gravity and cosmic Lorentz forces is not a well-trodden path? Of course, one would need to answer the basic question what electrically conductive liquid metal supersubstance flows everywhere in the universe leaving gravity behind in its cosmic wake which Einstein failed to do. He was close yet, inconsolable to the end on his death bed, could not make the required cognitive leap into the dissonant darkness to conceive of night as a ghostlike black haze of massive cold liquid droplets of this exotic conscious primordial entangled pre-baryonic superconductive uber-magnetic metal-alloy supersubstance raining down onto the sun from trillions of km away. Go figure!

THE MOON AND THE TIDES

According to my little theory, it would appear that Newton was incorrect about the tides while Descartes was spot on.

I conceive of the moon as a bubble of argon hydride floating in the upper exosphere of the earth and wholly contained within the greater neon hydride bubble surrounding each planet, too light to sink into the planetary host but too heavy to ever escape from it. The moon remains within the earth's gravity field while the tiny lunar gravity field is far removed from the earth's surface. Since gravity is a pushing and not a pulling force, the question is how can the moon possibly cause the high tides on the planet?

The answer is simple and elegant. As the moon rotates about the earth, its weight pushes down into the earth's atmosphere layers observing Pascal's Law and causing a pressure displacement on the surface. Thus, taking angular momentum into account, the moon causes directly not the high tides *but the low tides* with indirect lateral bulges on the sides.

CONCLUSIONS

I conclude that gravity-causing dark matter is the cold black liquid phase of whatever daytime sunshine really is which in turn is the white-hot glowing gas phase of whatever night really is.

Lo and behold, the Luminitherous Aeffer doth exist, after all, und Herr Einstein, you monumental bombastic clown, white light certainly requires a liquid medium in which to propagate as waves. To describe Licht as merely an electromagnetic wave propagating in a vacuum is fundamental bullshit. We are dealing here with a remarkable substance of matter existing around us in two distinct phases – hot and cold – with two distinct visible electromagnetic radiation emissions of light – white and black. That humanity in general and the sciences in particular have gotten it so wrong is a savage indictment and a clear indication, as if further evidence is required, that we are nothing but useless and exceedingly stupid cockroaches scurrying around blinded by the light feeding off our own waste products.

The very existence of this dominant non-baryonic photonic physical substance remains a mystery to the collective sciences although the cosmic wake it leaves behind is observable everywhere. Inexplicably, this enigmatic substance remains unidentified and elusive although many expensive attempts have been made to reveal it. Earlier more primitive humans recognized its hidden extra-dimensional existence and ascribed to it epithets of the Gods. To this day, calling it God appears the best and closest description. A long list of unexplained physical phenomena exists seeking its ultimate revelation and description. This list includes our dark mysterious night, quantum mechanics, gravity, dark matter, weather and sleep anomalies. Ironically although catastrophically overlooked until today, once one adopts a more correct and fundamental definition of this substance, one begins to see it everywhere. For the sake of simplicity and convenience, I have referred to it as Lightonium although, besides 'the good Lord above', it remains officially nameless.

Separated on the fractal scale, Lightonium and water share many similarities. Liquid water behaves on planets similarly to how liquid Lightonium acts on stars. Water switches constantly between liquid and gas phases as it follows Lightonium doing the same thing. Our night is the passage of cold liquid Lightonium heading to the sun and our day is the alternating flow of hot gas Lightonium coming off the sun.

The solar system glowing with electrically charged gas Lightonium is the equivalent of a glowing neon tube on a cosmic scale; instead of Time Square the entire solar system with a diameter of 30 billion km glows in the darkness!

Our visible black night is not nothing, after all, but something active in its own right. Rigorously testing this theory from a conceptual perspective led me to the conclusion that our dark night is visible black microwave electromagnetic radiation of light. This has forced a fundamental revision of sunlight and cosmological star creation explaining so-called Jean's Instability and answering the basic question how a cloud of gas and dust can possibly 'collapse' to form stars. Crucially, the existence of black cold liquid photons of light explains the Cosmic Microwave Background correctly once and for all.

We are dealing here with an ancient photonic physical substance of matter that fills our universe. It would be more correct to say that our young baryonic universe is entirely subsumed within the greater photon matrix arriving, as it were, as an after-thought excrescence. This photonic substance appears to be made from a very ancient, perhaps hundreds of billions of years old, metal-alloy substance exhibiting unique properties of electrical conductivity and magnetism with both hot and cold thermodynamic powers acting over untold mind-boggling distances. Since this substance behaves similarly to molecular baryonic substances like water, we can assume this is an equivalently 'molecular' pre-baryonic substance with equivalent properties of matter such as phase transition and visible emission of electromagnetic radiation according to its temperature. The laws of Conservation of Energy and Momentum apply equally to this pre-baryonic substance in both its hot gas and cold liquid phases.

Composed of bits so tiny we cannot hope to see nor measure them directly and possessing 'molecular' internal bonds entirely of a new order, this pre-baryonic substance appears to us as extra-dimensional operating in both micro and macro spaces beyond our direct grasp. Acting similarly to water on planets, this remarkable supersubstance is constantly changing phase from superliquid to supergas on the surface of stars at a constant boiling temperature of around 6000K. A superliquid less dense than hydrogen gas yet capable of exerting enough conserved momentum over the span of galaxies to create black holes!

Here on earth, we are confronted daily with two distinct equally visible passages of the stuff moving in different directions relative to the sun: falling cold liquid phase by night and rising hot gas phase by day.

White daytime light is the hot visible white spectrum electrically charged glowing gas phase of this substance blasting off the sun and black nighttime light is the cold visible black electrically charged glowing liquid phase of the same substance. Our day is the visible gas phase of night and our night is the visible liquid phase of day. There are two visible spectra of light, one white spectrum and one black microwave spectrum. Like us peeps, light also arrives in both white and black quanta packages.

The wave/particle duality of light points directly to the two naturally occurring phase states of light – expanding exploding waves of gas phase photon bubbles and contracting imploding particles of liquid phase haze-like

photon droplets. It is this previously unidentified bosonic supersubstance that accounts for gravity and dark matter and must account for the incorrectly interpreted Cosmic Microwave Background as well.

Why this fundamental fact has eluded the entire scientific community since Akhenaten and Nefertiti at the dawn of recorded time is quite simply beyond the scope of this essay and is more difficult to peg down than the existence of visible black photons of light themselves.

The many observable similarities between how water behaves on planets and how this supersubstance behaves on stars is the key to unlocking quantum gravity and many other unexplained phenomena of the night including ghosts and vampires. The identification of visible black light finally reveals the fundamental nature of the wave/particle duality of light.

I have described galaxies and solar systems as closed energy loop systems as described by the First Law of Thermodynamics. I have proposed that cosmic liquid oceans of helium hydride in the furthest reaches of space absorb and discharge vast amounts of electricity and power the cosmic flow of cold gravity-forming liquid Lightonium.

This essay calls for the entire theory about light to be re-written to include the existence of the visible particle function massive black photon of light, the quantum gauge boson of gravity, the subatomic particle of dark matter and the real band behind the CMB.

A compelling reason to accept the existence of the visible black photon of light is the long list of phenomena explained by its presence. This list includes the duality of light, quantum gravity, dark matter, the CMB and the Hubble tension, Olbers' Paradox and our black night, weather and many sleep anomalies.

If there remains any chance whatsoever of saving our home planet and turning the tide of catastrophic global warming, it is imperative now more than ever to identify the cold black phase of light itself and for science to start pulling in the other direction. Additionally, since all natural dualities are inherently and fundamentally connected, the formal identification of the visible black photon will also resolve the social ills of racism and patriarchy – embedded in both humanity and the sciences – immediately!

Identifying the cold black photon field of light explains why both patriarchy and racism are embedded in the sciences and everywhere else. Emergent dualities like the male/female duality found throughout the plant and animal kingdoms of life are intimately connected to the fundamental duality of light – as below so above. The duality of light points directly to the two atavistic primordial energy force fields in nature: hot white light as patriarchal and cold black light as matriarchal. Not in the moon but in the very power of the black night is where our universal mama lurks. Witches always knew this fundamental 'heresy', often paying the ultimate price for it, and now you do too.

By failing to identify the cold black light of night, both black people and women are forever relegated to the back seat of society and second class citizens. How absurd that both racism and sexism are applied even to photons of light!!!

Taken together with a pinch of good old-fashioned common sense logic, the ubiquitous light/dark cycle in nature, the quantum duality of light, the 1st law of thermodynamics and Orkadmon's law, one should be able to arrive without much fuss at the conclusion that if one quantum photon boson of electromagnetism exists then two photon bosons of electromagnetism exist; namely, the present exploding wave function white hot energy transporting gas phase massless daytime photon bubble of light and the errant imploding particle function black cold momentum transporting liquid phase massive nighttime photon raindrop of light.

PROPOSED TESTS

My theory rests on proving that our night is visible black light emitted by gravity causing dark matter. It seems self-evident to me that if night is indeed the second active photon field on earth, our brains conscious or otherwise, *must* know about it. Seek and ye shall find! My proposal to prove the existence of nightly black light

is to locate it in our own brains. One or two billion dollars should be sufficient to follow all evident brain patterns and anomalies to confirm the black photon's presence and existence. Universal nightly drooping brain behavior, sleep, depolarizing dark current, deep sleep brain activity, REM and dreams all combine to point directly at an unidentified but active black photon field of light throughout the night.

A fresh study of rain looking at the proposed black photon liquid drop as the universal raindrop nucleator is another area that might surely provide real solutions to both gravity and dark matter. In addition, I call on theoretical physicists to come up with innovative ideas to prove that our night is indeed visible black light. The CMB, understood correctly, provides the real demonstrable evidence to support my hypothesis. Is it possible to connect the CMB directly with the passage of night to correct this blight of modern physics and cosmology? Spend another billion on investigating the alleged wave/particle duality of water and the fundamental connection between water and light and, hey presto, Bob's your aunty!

According to Google, the proof of electromagnetic radiation of light is being able to see it. The night appears both visible and black in color and why is this not sufficient? Coupled with the visible boiling and bubbling solar surface should be a slam dunk. Observable phenomena and common sense logic should prevail to confirm that sunlight, whatever it is, constantly changes phase on the solar surface and is itself glowing photon gas.

ORKADMON'S LAW OF UNIVERSAL BLACK PHOTON GRAVITO-ELECTROMAGNETOHYDRODYNAMICS

Follow the nucleating polar covalent liquid hydrides in general and water in particular to locate the cold visible cosmic microwave ground-state non-local momentum-conserving gravity-unifying positively-charged particle function liquid-phase star-bound massive-raindrop black photon corpuscle of light, the real God-particle of the universe, the subatomic particle of dark matter, the quantum gauge boson of gravity, the universal raindrop nucleator and the purveyor of dreams.

In closing, I dedicate my formal identification of the gravity causing black light of night to Madiba, the last real man of history.